

Literature and Society” The Role of Literature in social change

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Abstract:

Literature is intimately related to society. Viewed as a whole, a body of literature is part of the entire culture of a people. Its themes and problems emerge from group activities and group situations, and its significance lies in the extent to which it expresses and enriches the totality of culture. It is an integral part of the entire culture tied by a tissue of connection with every other element in the culture. A society is a group of people involved in persistent social interaction. Society influences literature in many ways and the connection of the Literature with society are integral and pervasive. Through this paper I will be focusing on how literature is helpful to society. Highlighting the commitment of literature to society and how literature actually reflects the society.

Keywords: Literature, Culture, entire, Society, commitment, integral.

Introduction:

Literature is the other name of life. It reflects the society, its good values and its evils. Literature mirrors the evils of the society to highlight the mistakes and make amends for it. It also projects good values in the society for people to follow. Literature, as an imitation of human action, presents a picture of what people think, say, and do in the society. In Literature, we find stories designed to portray human life and action through some characters who convey certain messages for the purpose of education, information and entertainment by their words, actions, and reactions. Thus, Literature is not only a reflection of the society but also serves as a corrective mirror in which members of the society can look at literature. So it is necessary to take a close look at some works of literature in order to understand how literature actually reflects the society and tries to reform it.

Literature is closely related to society as it is directly associated with its culture and tradition. The poet, the dramatist, the novelist or the essayist are all the product of their age and their age openly and clearly gets imaged in their compositions. Its themes and subjects emerge from the problems related with the society to which it belongs. It basically shows us the different facets of society helping us to understand man and his problems. The range of social influences on literature is as broad as the prevailing system of class structure, economy, political. Organization and the socio-cultural ideas prevailing in a system. Every literary figure is an exponent of his society and always tries to propagate the values, deficiencies and important issues of the society to which he belongs. A good writer is not only influenced by the society around him but he also influences it with his moral vision and opinion regarding a noble society. The writer is the one who not only exposes the vices of people before them but also helps them to be influenced by it and mould them according to the writer's point of

view. It can be said that almost every piece of art related with society is a social document through which a writer tries to exhibit his philosophy regarding the social morality which actually in his real target. Thus, every work of literature which is social work is based on social morality.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study how literature is intimately related to society.
2. To study how literature is helpful to society.
3. To study the role of literature in social change and how literature actually reflects the society.

Research Methodology:-

The present paper is basically descriptive in nature and the data used in this paper is purely from secondary sources especially collected from internet, You Tube, published papers and books.

Literature as a mirror of society:

Literature means something that is written for refreshing and inspiring the mind. It records the thoughts and feelings of great minds. Literature enriches the mind and reading as they say makes as man perfect. Literary works are portrayals of thinking patterns and social norms prevalent in society. Literature introduces us to new worlds of experience. We learn about books and literature, we enjoy the comedies and the tragedies of poems stories and plays and we may even grow and evolve through our literary journey with books. Literature is the foundation of life. It places on emphasis on many topics from human tragedies to tales of the ever-popular search for love. Mirror has the unique quality of being honest. It reflects whatever it sees without evolution. Like mirror literature helps to make a clear assessment of what is wrong and what needs to be done to better the society. The contribution of literature to any given society is immense. Literature has the capacity to mould the thinking of a whole age as it is the mirror of the society. Literature reflects the development of society and people in their compositions which

helps us to classify them into various periods. Literature is also a mode to express public opinion in variety of genres. It tells us of our rich culture and gives us a sense of pride in our country. In short, we can say literature is the light house of any culture as it gives us a true picture of the culture and its development.

Literature and social change:-

Literature and social change have a unique relationship. Literature is an effective tool for social change. Man is doing the work of social change through his hard work, speech and writing. To achieve this process of transformation, many social reforms and intellectuals have adopted the above media as a tool. Social work is needed for social change. This struggle happens through social revolution. Literature is doing the job of providing energy to this social revolution. Literature of the highest quality is bound by principles that give dignity to man. Literature with ideas that inculcate sustainable ethics and human life values in the society. The process of creating the social system based on life values and ethical values by overturning the inferior traditions, thought systems, religious system, culture etc. in the society is called social transformation. This process of social change is a process of all out struggle for human literature. In the process of social transformation the complete destruction of injustice arising from social, economic, religious, and political disparities in the society is considered. When a society does not treat its various elements with justice, equality, and respect, the need for social revolution arises. This revolution does not only touch the superficial part of social life but also seeks to radically change the social system by touching the overall elements. Therefore, to speed up the social transformation, it is necessary to adopt the weapon of social revolutions.

The best quality literature is realized from life experiences. Freedom, social justice, economic equality, fraternity, humanity are the values of life which are seen to be invented from such literature. Cultivation of knowledge and ideas along with art is seen in Literature. The reflection of good and bad tendencies in society, class struggle can be seen through literature. New ideas are discussed through literary efforts. Among them, Dalit literature is very important literary stream. Dalit literature has been silently suffering injustice and oppression since centuries. The human liberation movement started by Babasaheb Ambedkar woke up and began to search for its existence. He participated in the movement for human liberation. Man is a social animal and depends upon society to develop and acquire his full potentials. Obviously, Literature mirrors the manners and morals that form the cornerstones of a society and help it become efficient and effective.

The Role of Literature in social change:-

It would be appropriate to highlight the commitment of literature to society and the commitment of the society to literature. When Mathew Arnold says that poetry is cultural criticism and writer makes a close examination and comment on the society. The role of the writer behind this commentary is that the society should adopt the good part of it. Another meaning of this is that literature is nothing but means of expressing society. Good culture comes from literature. Literature is the mirror of society. What happens in a society is reflected in Literary works in one form or another. The literal meaning of Literature is the art of written work in different forms, such as poetry, plays, stories, prose, fiction etc. Literature is the foundation of life. It places an emphasis on many topics from human tragedies. Literature enables people to see through the lenses of others. Ultimately, literature has provided a gateway to teach the reader about life experiences from even the saddest stories to the most joyful ones that will touch their hearts.

The role of literature in changing society is immense. Mahatma Phule's revolutionary work is unique. Phule discussed the causes of social, economic, religious disparity and exploitation through books like Slavery, Peasant's Asud etc. After Mahatma Phule, in the 20th century an era of social revolution dawned in the form of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar. For the upliftment of Dalit, Dr. Ambedkar's literature is an invaluable contribution. Through his newspapers – Muknayak, Samata, Janata, Bahiskrut Bharat etc. as well as books like 'Who Were the Shudras', Buddha and his Dhamma etc. He did the work of agilitarian society by expressing scientific progressive thoughts. In our country there are many authors who wrote about their land, culture and people of the society. R.K. Narayan, Munshi Premchand, Mulk Raj Anand and Raja Rao are the founding fathers of Indian literature were mainly concerned with the downtrodden of the society. The Indian authors have touched each and every aspect of Indian Life. They have portrayed the beautiful picture of India through their writings and because of it the culture, tradition and values of our country got such a high recognition in the world context. Munshi Premchand showed the actual Indian society. The time when India was almost rural place, Premchand in his works tried to show that what he observed in those days of India. R.K Narayan has risen to become the second most famous Indian Novelist writing in English. In the novels of R K Narayan, one can find the true representation of contemporary Indian life, culture in its clear and realistic form. His novel 'Guide' reveals the Indian way of life and also the culture and tradition of India. Through his novel 'Guide' he has given a true social feature of India.

The traits of Indian manners and customs are reflected. In the history of Indian fiction, the most prominent writer Mulk Raj Anand's 'Untouchable' is a symbolic Seg of the miserable lives of the millions of untouchables in India. Thus, Literature creates society. In short, we can say Literature has a major impact on the development of society.

Conclusion:-

Achieving social change through literature is not a easy task. The common people have to be made to struggle by showing the evil entry in the society. In doing so, literature faces major challenges. Bitter opposition from critics has to be indured. But literature has overcome all such obstacles and done the work of human liberation and social transformation. The growth of human civilization is closely related to the growth of literature. So, naturally human society is also related to literature. In every part of the word, literature has been more or less, mirror of society as it reflects the societies values. Literature can positively influence people's minds and attitude and can inspire people to act for the welfare of society. It can also be a tool for creating empathy, allowing people to understand the perspectives of others. No-doubt, Literature can work to change the society as it helps us better understand our lives, ourselves and the word around us. In short, one cannot imagine the progress of society without literature as it makes us to deeply analyze, societal issues and also provides us a solution to solve problems.

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